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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
AC	Advisory Council on Youth
AGO	Agora Brussels
AI Hungary	Amnesty International Hungary
AJL	Assemblée libre des jeunes

BDCs	Brussels Deliberative Committees
Brexit	Brexit referendum
CONSUL	Consul Democracy
CYA	Children and Youth Assembly in Scotland and Ireland
DC	Deliberative Committees in Brussels
DCDM	Decidim
DEC	Declic
DIs	Democratic Innovations
DO	Democratic Odyssey
EAFT-ECI	"Ending the Aviation Fuel Tax Exemption in Europe" ECI
EC	European Commission
EH	EurHope
EJWSK	Europa, jetzt wird's konkret!
EUJD	EU Youth Dialogue
EYT	EU Youth Test
FAF	Forum against Fakes
FC	French Convention (temps de l'enfant)
FCTC	France's Convention on the Time of the Child
FFF	Fridays for Future
HTV	Howtheyvote.eu
IWTM	Tanítanék Mozgalom ("I Would Teach Movement", Hungary)
MAKE	Make.org
MCA	Moldova Citizens Assembly
MOJ	Moj Grad
MSK	Młodzieżowy Strajk Klimatyczny (Fridays for Future Poland)
MZA	mZaednica
OBM	Burgerdialog Ostbelgien
OSP	Open Source Politics
RPS	Refondation du Parti Socialiste
TREE	Treecompany.be
Vote16	Lowering the voting age
YCAIIV	Youth Climate Assembly in Ida-Viru

Abstract

In this article we argue that the current proliferation of democratic innovations risks masking a deeper failure: the absence of meaningful pathways between participation and power. Democratic renewal will not come from multiplying participatory processes, but from identifying which participatory chains link voice to influence, and deliberation to decision. Without such chains, participation fragments and dissipates; with them, it can cumulate into real democratic power.

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Introduction

How societies observe, contest and reshape the values underpinning their democratic systems is a perennial concern of both scholarship and political practice. Today, however, these debates have acquired renewed urgency. Major geopolitical disruptions, ranging from democratic backsliding to the fracturing of the rules-based order, have unsettled long-held assumptions about the resilience and universality of “democracy”. The question is no longer simply whether democracy will endure, but how it can be renewed to address these challenges.

For decades, this question was framed through a binary lens opposing “democratic” to “authoritarian” regimes, often reduced to a checklist of institutional features or normative attributes. Democracy as both an ideal and a practice, refers to a plurality of experiences across time and space, encompassing diverse epistemologies, institutional forms and constellations of actors across the globe. What is at stake today is less a defence of a fixed model than the reinvention of democratic practices capable of sustaining meaningful citizens power under conditions of complexity and contestation.

It is in this spirit that the burgeoning field of democratic innovations (DIs) has sought to reimagine the relationship between citizens and power. As explored under our research project YouthDecide2040, DIs understood as “new or reconfigured participatory practices designed to deepen the link between citizen input and political authority” have proliferated across contexts, from citizens assemblies and participatory budgeting to grassroots digital platforms and party democratisation¹. Yet their expansion has not followed a linear trajectory. Rather, DIs have evolved unevenly through technological environments, institutional settings or political cultures, producing a fragmented landscape.

This proliferation poses an epistemological and normative challenge. As recent scholarship in the ‘Sciences of Democracies’ suggests, understanding contemporary democratic change requires moving beyond isolated case studies towards more integrated and critical analyses, as well as a comparative and cross-border lens (Gagnon and Abrams, eds, 2025). Moreover, a critical perspective highlights that DIs, taken individually, often struggle to generate sustainable impact, raising questions about their capacity to move beyond localised experimentation towards systemic transformation.

This is also the spirit animating authors who have explored the idea of “democratic assemblages” whereby new democratic practices emerge in very different spaces, engage a range of voices, including non-humans, and are generally organised over a period of time in which socio-political environments might change as the DIs themselves are deployed. Assemblage theory (Asenbaum and Bussu, 2025) accounts for such unpredictability and posits that all-society democratic renewal originates from a combination of factors and actors. It encourages us to observe the complexity of imagining future democratic ecosystems that fully harness their intrinsic epistemic power, while identifying the most suited correctives to inequality and disempowerment. Our contribution is inspired by this line of scholarship but tries to situate human agency more systematically in these dynamics and from there to propose a more formal way of analysing the combinations that we are all interested in through the building blocks of democratic innovations.

Further, in this article, we argue that democratic renewal depends not on the proliferation of isolated democratic innovations, but on their articulation into participatory chains that connect citizens to power across time, scales, and institutions. We introduce the concept of participatory chains to capture how different democratic innovations can be sequenced, combined and embedded across institutional, societal and geographical settings and thus become mutually self-reinforcing.

¹ See for instance the more extended definition by Elstub and Escobar of DIs as “processes or institutions that are new to a policy issue, policy role of level of governance and developed to reimagine and deepen the role of citizens in governance processes by increasing opportunities of participation, deliberation and influence” (2019, pp.11)

By linking participatory practices over time and across arenas, such participatory chains can transform isolated moments of engagement or episodic consultations into sustained processes of empowerment, learning, and political influence. This explains why many well-designed democratic innovations remain politically marginal, while others generate systemic effects. Democratic renewal, in this view, is not the product of discrete interventions, but of an evolving ecosystem in which participation circulates, accumulates, and translates into power. By foregrounding relational structures, the participatory chain captures a process of translation where the challenge is not to innovate more, but to connect better.

This argument deepens but also departs from the mainstream literature on democratic innovations, which has extensively examined individual DIs and, non-systematically, the commonalities in sequencing them. Moreover, it allows us to foreground the structurally distinctive position of youth participation which frequently traverses informal and formal modes of engagement, often located at points of translation between democratic arenas and digital mobilisation, street-level activism, and institutionalised participatory forums.

Youth social movements and activist networks play an important integrative role within democratic innovation ecosystems. Such movements are dynamic arenas in which new claims, repertoires of participation, and normative expectations are articulated and tested, some of which enter more mainstream institutional channels. This becomes analytically significant because it prefigures how participatory inputs travel across levels, sectors, and sites of participation, and how new repertoires enter institutional settings. Our research agenda has sought to mirror this fluid reality by traveling in time and space, spanning different social contexts and institutional landscapes. While we focus on European case studies, we refer to a selection of European examples with an eye to drawing from best practices as they are tested in different contexts, as we seek to and 'reverse the gaze' (Nicolaidis and Youngs, 2023).

Building on this conceptual approach, our theoretical claim is that the political impact of participatory chains depends on a combination of three factors: context, the quality of connections between DIs and optimal design, be it spontaneous or formal. Systemic change emerges through more or less formal interconnectedness among citizens, grassroots movements, civil society actors, administrative bodies, and political decision-makers. The participatory chain functions as the mechanism through which multi-stakeholder inputs travel across scales and over time, gain authority, and become actionable. Without such cross-sectoral and cross-scalar coupling, participatory processes remain isolated and politically peripheral.

The article proceeds in three steps. First, we situate the rise of democratic innovations within the broader diagnosis of democratic stagflation, characterised by the simultaneous proliferation of participatory practices and their limited transformative impact. Second, we present three exemplary archetypes of participatory chains and proceed to map the main families of democratic innovations that constitute them. Third, we analyse examples of participatory chains linking these innovations across time, institutions, and levels of governance. In doing so, we outline the conditions under which democratic innovations can move from isolated experiments to a coherent ecosystem capable of sustaining meaningful democratic renewal.

Part I: Youth and ‘democratic stagflation’

Reframing “losers’ consent” in electoral democracies

Electoral democracy remains the primary pathway through which political power is contested and collective futures negotiated. But the current era of democratic disillusionment exposes the inherent fragilities of a model of liberal democracy centred on electoral competition. The Schumpeterian vision of democracy as competition among elites mediated by political parties, has long rested on the assumption that enlightened elites can adjudicate between competing social interests and aspirations (Schumpeter, 1942. Dean, 2016). But this assumption obscures more than ever the persistent risks of capture that plague democratic life. As Robert Dahl observed, “The most highly privileged members of a society – the political, social and economic elites, if you will typically espouse and, when they can, even enforce doctrines that justify their superiority” (2010, pp25).

The institutional scaffolding designed to integrate younger generations into electoral politics, should not blind us to these structural limits (Coman and Brack 2025). Across many democracies, we are witnessing not merely dissensus within politics, but growing dissensus about politics itself.

Liberal democracies are increasingly put on trial on multiple fronts. Materialist critiques highlight the contradictions between democratic equality and entrenched inequalities under neoliberal capitalism. At the same time, the old Platonic advocacy of guardianship and expertise as the drivers of progress is never far behind, as claims regarding the technical complexity of economic governance mask its redistributive and therefore political nature. And we are left with the pervasive question: What can be the democratic counter to the subsequent rise of “techno-populism” or co-dependency between technocratic rule and populist demagogues (Bickerton, 2022, Mattei, 2024)? Against this backdrop, youth engagement offers a particularly revealing lens. For one, the young generation, at least those involved in various kinds of engagement seem acutely conscious of the structural obstacles they face, from capitalist division of labour to the continued illusion of boundless neoliberal bounties, paired with the promise of the self-regulatory markets. Even among a very different constituency - say youth with a strong belief in neoliberal policies - we find pervasive disaffection from traditional politics.

As a result, the overrepresentation of youth in activism - from the Global Justice Movement to the post-2008 anti-austerity protests - signals not apathy but a clear malaise with traditional political channels and their incapacity to address these obstacles ([Chironi, della Porta and Milan, 2024](#)). Young people increasingly seek to negotiate alternative futures outside institutionalised party systems, drawing on their experience of disempowerment in the poli-crisis, and the perceived incapacity of electoral and party-based politics to address long term challenges.

These dynamics are also further shaped for many by insights from feminist and post-colonial thought which foregrounds the enduring prevalence of patriarchy, colonial legacies and entrenched racism. Many among the young see these forces as shaping not only policies and their outcomes but the rules of the game themselves. These are often called “structural” forces because they permeate the ways those in power think and the ways they shape these rules. Unsurprisingly, when the same social, economic, geographic, ethnic or religious groups always seem to be on the same (losing or winning) side, undermines the core premise of electoral democracy: loser’s consent, namely that one accepts defeat today in the expectation of winning tomorrow. This assumption in turn is premised on the idea that winning and losing coalitions are not fixed but reconfigured with different issues over different periods.

The erosion of loser’s consent is thus emerging as a structural feature of contemporary democratic crises. For younger generations in particular, the persistence of democratic pathologies such as vast inequalities and systemic exclusions raise fundamental doubts about the responsiveness of traditional democratic institutions. Tinkering at the margin seems utterly insufficient (Gagnon, Shah and Kelly, 2025). In this context, calls for greater inclusion are not merely procedural but speak to deeper questions of empowerment. Yet existing participatory opportunities often fail to meet such expectations. This is especially pertinent to youth, who tend to mobilise around single issues (Markowski and Zagórski, 2025) while mainstream political debates remain focussed on around electoral competition and rights, rather than substantive disagreements over long-term trade-offs to policy choices (Coman and Brack, 2025).

We are not speaking here of the kind of withholding of loser’s consent that drove Trump or Bolsonaro’s support to storm their respective institutions and outright refuse the result of electoral processes. Instead, we identify a more insidious process, a moral and political strain on loser’s consent, an erosion rather than outright rejection which weakens the idea of elections as the sole site of representation.

Short of their paroxysmic Trumpian expression, such tensions are especially visible in the highly polarised context of the US, where affective polarisation reinforces the erosion of loser’s consent. For many young people, particularly those of racially marginalised background, activism becomes both a political strategy and a form of psychological self-defence mechanism against full-scale disempowerment, a way to reclaim political space and mitigate the effects of systematic oppression on mental health (Anyiwo et al, 2020).

At the same time, counter-hegemonic movements on the right mobilise grievances around recognition and ‘status resurgence’, as seen in the rhetoric of movements such as MAGA (Koenig and Mendelberg, 2025). Across the political spectrum, a shared

dynamic emerges: a growing perception that the system is structurally biased and that electoral competition alone cannot redress this imbalance. Even if, from a different perspective, this is also how young people tend to experience the political discourses of traditional parties, which fail to address democratic pathologies like soaring inequalities.

This raises a fundamental question: can loser's consent be sustained when one is stuck indefinitely on the same losing side? Electoral democracy alone struggles to answer this question when the gap widens between what is at stake, such as inequality or climate futures, and the prevailing policies for distributing costs and benefits. In short, "if our social spheres are predominantly characterized by non-democracy, should it really be any surprise that liberal, electoral, and representative democracies are said to be fading in countries across the globe by those who have risen to the challenge of measuring them?" (Gagnon, Abrams et al. (2025, pp.19)

This predicament is compounded in the European context where contrary to many countries in the Global South, youth are also a statistical minority and are frequently framed in elite discourse as either disengaged or politically immature. Such narratives tend to become self-fulfilling prophecies to justify top-down agenda-setting which in turn discourages youth participation in traditional politics or civil service. They aggravate youth disempowerment and sharpen rhetorical instruments that limit their agency (Giugni and Grasso, 2025).

In Europe, new political actors like Spain's Podemos and Italy's 5 Star Movement (M5S) alongside earlier experiment like the German Pirate Party have attempted to respond through anti-establishment rhetoric, open membership approaches and their targeting of single-issue voters (Russo, Riera and Verthé, 2017; Gomez and Ramiro, 2019). These cases point to trends in electoral democracy, where losers' consent will depend increasingly on parties' capacity to deliver their electorates' political expectations, including by opening intra-party participatory processes. Here lies an initial bridge between traditional electoral politics and democratic innovations. But they also reveal a limit: such efforts remain uneven, fragile, and often insufficient to transform systemic dynamics. Where do we go from here?

'Democratic stagflation' and the pathways to DIs

Against this backdrop, one might have expected a flourishing of alternative pathways to 'people power', yet the reality is more sobering. In our view, contemporary democracies are suffering from what we call, borrowing from the economic lexicon, 'democratic stagflation', a situation in which participatory expectations expand while institutional responsiveness and legitimacy stagnate. This mismatch generates a persistent gap between the promise of participation and its tangible effects, without necessarily leading to regime breakdown.

Democratic stagflation manifests in multiple ways: although democratic innovations have proliferated (Smith, 2009), scholarship shows that access to participatory and deliberative arenas remains socially uneven and can reproduce existing exclusions.

As emergency politics continue to take central stage, political institutions continue to increase the direct and hidden political costs of participation. As a result, innovators cut on quality, DI “consumption” by citizens decreases, and DIs are standardised to the cheapest standards. Participatory quality stagnates, intersectional and politically sensitive issues are mostly left to the world of protest, while DIs are predominantly focused on single issues. Institutional attempts at deploying democratic innovations are not structurally connected to the actual policies of decision-making bodies. When they are, these are predominantly deployed with a consultative logic and do not require empirically demonstrable follow-up. There is minimal innovation, the incentives to participate (i.e. akin to wages in stagflation) are low and the priorities to participate (i.e. akin to low consumer demand) are reduced by material constraints of citizens (time, overall trade-offs of participating).

How then can we imagine exiting such democratic stagflation? Allow us to run with the democratic stagflation metaphor a bit further. Classically, there would need to be meaningful *tightening of democratic policy* (i.e. akin to fiscal policy in stagflation). As democratic costs of participation increase due to lack of credible and sustained follow-up amid geopolitical crises, reducing instances of citizen participation may seem like a plausible short-term intervention to safeguard the future expansions of participatory capacity on new grounds, to rebuild trust and reliability.

More constructively, we could expect widespread *inclusion adjustments* (i.e. akin to fiscal adjustments), targeted measures to address the democratic gaps that emerge for the most vulnerable, ensuring they are protected from (democratic) hardship and can equally intervene in the democratic life of the polity. We can also envisage *supply-side interventions*. Investing in developing and piloting new ways of imagining DI applications and ‘importing’ more from elsewhere, with an eye to experimenting with what works best.

An alternative path could consist in a *laissez-faire approach towards DIs self-regulation*. Allowing DIs to develop, with the belief that supply and demand of DIs will regulate autonomously. This would rest on the belief that the salience of democratic innovations will prove itself worthy of bottom-up empowerment and top-down norm adoption through systemic demand/supply mechanisms.

Finally, a more ambitious - and yet time-bound - exit strategy would be to design *strategic interventions on credibility* (i.e. akin to intervening to stabilise international market credibility). This would mean intervening at the level of communication and advocacy, to avoid further inflation on the material and immaterial costs of un-fulfilled DI expectations by ensuring that private actors and institutions and other stakeholders in DIs offer credible growth stimuli. In sum, in times of ‘democratic stagflation’, the range of actors that mobilise towards effectiveness and productivity of DIs is critical, just as much as the range of actors that buy-into a long-term strategy.

Part II: Participatory chains of democratic innovations

Where then can we expect variations on how, when and where we tackle democratic stagflation? In our view, there are many participatory chains which can start to respond to this need. Part II starts by setting out three particular but archetypal participatory chains which our research has identified as most promising avenues for lasting democratic change anchored in meaningful social dynamics. This is not to say of course, that they are the only ones, only that we have identified them as key findings. We then go back to the building blocks of these participatory chains, assessing the extent to which they contribute meaningfully to opening up youth engagement.

Archetypal Participatory Chains

1. **Insurgent-to-Institutional chains:** originate in moments of mobilisation led by social movements and informal civil society actors, where grievances, claims, and alternative visions are first articulated outside formal political arenas. But faced with their own limits, these insurgent dynamics can give rise to deliberative processes like assemblies, forums, or coordinated campaigns, that transform diffuse demands into more structured collective judgements. The defining feature of this chain is its trajectory towards progressive institutionalisation through increasingly binding mechanisms, including instruments of direct democracy such as citizens' initiatives or even referenda. In this way, bottom-up mobilisation is not confined to protest or voice, but culminates in the formalisation of outputs within the political system. The democratic promise of this chain lies in its capacity to convert social legitimacy into legal authority. Its challenge resides in maintaining inclusiveness and deliberative integrity as movements scale and enter institutional channels.

2. **Counter-Power Chains:** initiated by informal networks of civic oversight that aim to function as permanent or semi-permanent watchdogs over political authority. They include investigative collectives of journalists (e.g. 'Follow the Money'), transparency platforms, civic tech initiatives, and activist monitoring networks that generate continuous scrutiny over decision-makers. Rather than emerging from episodic mobilisation, these chains operate through sustained information flows and accountability mechanisms, exposing failures, tracking commitments, and informing public debate. Such dynamics can trigger direct democratic interventions, such as petitions, recalls, referend, which, in turn, reshape political competition and contribute to processes of electoral renewal. Their strength lies in the construction of distributed accountability, where citizens act not only as participants but as ongoing monitors of power – a vast infrastructure constituting a “democratic panopticon.” (Nicolaidis, 2021). Yet their effectiveness depends on their capacity to channel scrutiny into constructive political pathways, avoiding fragmentation, distrust, or purely oppositional dynamics.

3. **Viral Deliberation Chains:** emerge from waves of participation accelerated by digital and direct democratic practices, where engagement spreads rapidly across networks

through campaigns, platforms, or mass consultations or mandatory follow-up. What distinguishes this chain is its ability to scale-up speed-up participation into structured deliberation: initial bursts of participation are channelled into deliberative processes, such as citizens' assemblies or hybrid forums, that refine and prioritise collective inputs. Crucially, these processes are coupled with institutionalised commitments to follow-up, ensuring that outcomes are not merely consultative but feed into decision-making by public authorities and other democratic stakeholders. The democratic potential of viral deliberation lies in its capacity to bridge mass participation and considered judgment. Its central risk is that rapid mobilisation may outpace deliberative depth unless carefully designed and embedded.

Taken together, these three chains should not be understood as competing models, but as complementary pathways within a broader participatory ecosystem. *Insurgent-to-Institutional chains* provide the initial energy and normative impetus, transforming social mobilisation into binding political outcomes. *Counter-power chains* sustain democratic vigilance over time, ensuring that authority remains accountable and responsive beyond moments of mobilisation. *Viral deliberation chains*, in turn, enable participation to scale and circulate, linking mass engagement with structured deliberation and institutional follow-up. When articulated together, these chains can reinforce one another: insurgent mobilisation feeds oversight, oversight informs deliberation, and deliberation channels both into decision-making.

Conversely, when they remain disconnected, participation risks fragmentation - oscillating between protest without impact, scrutiny without consequence, and engagement without follow-through. Democratic renewal, we suggest, depends precisely on the capacity to weave these chains into coherent participatory systems, allowing citizen power to travel across arenas, accumulate over time, and ultimately shape collective outcomes.

Mapping families of democratic innovations

In order to dig deeper into the genealogies of these democratic chains, we now explore a range of DIs regrouped into separate families and ask how they are deployed to eventually form participatory chains. Such a mapping leads us to analyse the potentially synergetic relationships that can occur among them and which lead to participatory chains. We identify five main families of DIs (Gaiba, Hoppe, Moskovic, Nicolaidis, Pellegrini, and Zgut-Przybylska, 2025): electoral democracy; deliberative democracy; digital democracy; direct democracy; social movements and activism.

i. Electoral democracy

In our view, the crisis of election-based democracy discussed in Part I does not call for its replacement. Instead, elections will recover their democratic pedigree if designed for synergies. We do so through three contrasting cases: state-led institutional reform, with Austria's 2007 reform lowering the voting age from 18 to 16. Party organisational renewal with the Belgian Socialist Party's ongoing 'refoundation' process. And bottom-up intervention into parliamentary representation with Agora Brussels, a citizen-led

initiative that sought to connect elected representatives in the Brussels Parliament to a permanent Citizens' Assembly.

These cases capture three different transformative logics and provide interesting insights on how participatory chains can potentially amplify youth engagement. The Belgian Socialist Party launched citizen consultations on party values, internal procedures, and priorities after electoral decline. But it is hard to imagine this process having a long-term impact divorced from the kind of dynamic which we described under the “*viral deliberation*” chains. Nor are these citizens expected to provide the necessary level of scrutiny to qualify as part of “*counter-power chains*”.

The Austrian case broadened the formal electorate through constitutional change. It represents a strategy of scale: lowering the voting age enfranchised all 16- and 17-year-olds as a response to concerns about youth underrepresentation in an ageing society. This is where the insurgent-to-Institutional chains can become extremely relevant, when we think of adolescent youth involved in the process. Owing to the insight that legal inclusion offered by a lower voting age is insufficient, the reform was accompanied by awareness-raising and civic education, but both the interview material and the relevant literature suggest that meaningful youth engagement depends on softer infrastructures such as peer-to-peer contact, political socialisation, and sustained opportunities for participation beyond the vote itself. Recent evidence further tempers celebratory interpretations by questioning whether voting at 16 generates durable turnout effects over time (Aichholzer and Kritzing, 2020; Graf et al., 2024). It is a measure of inclusion, but not one that addresses substantive non-representation wholesale, a deficit that might be addressed by tacking on ‘viral deliberation chains’ to voting reforms.

Finally, Agora Brussels infused deliberative practices directly into representative politics, while also generating a substantial parliamentary track record between 2019 and 2024, with 246 parliamentary actions emerging from it. The case study of Agora Brussels is important in this sense, as it sought to foster substantive depth. Notably, it did not seek mass youth mobilisation, but proportional inclusion supported by informal meetings, confidence-building, and community-oriented spaces that fostered belonging and longer-term political activation among young participants. In this sense its impact on youth engagement could still be magnified if embedded into deliberation chains or even give birth to counter-power chains.

For processes where the mainstreaming of youth participation is relatively advanced, such as citizens' assemblies, the inclusion of age groups starting at 16 years old is already being piloted, while it is quite mainstreamed for young people over 18. Conversely, as it pertains to the inclusion of children in intergenerational participatory processes, which is yet far from being mainstreamed, the very presence of children can signal a first step towards more meaningful inclusion (Lundy, 2018) and an anchor of what we have argued deliberation's strong suit: negotiating collective futures. Taken together, the three case studies point to the fact that youth participation in electoral democracy should be evaluated not only by whether young people are present, but by whether reforms balance breadth, depth, and substantive influence.

ii. Deliberative democracy

We examined four case studies in (i) the Brussels Deliberative Committees (BDCs), which since 2019 have embedded joint deliberation by randomly selected citizens and MPs into parliamentary procedure; (ii) the Youth Assemblies in Ireland and Scotland, which were explicitly designed to centre children and young people in climate and biodiversity debates; (iii) France's Convention on the Time of the Child (FCTC), which integrates children and teenagers into deliberation on everyday issues such as school rhythms and wellbeing; and (iv) the Democratic Odyssey, a travelling People's Assembly piloted across Athens, Florence, and Vienna as a prototype for a transnational European assembly. We look at how deliberative innovations seek to renew democracy across different scales, from regional parliaments to transnational civil-society experiments. Together, these cases move from institutionalised to experimental designs, and from adult-centred to youth-inclusive deliberation.

A central observation is that youth inclusion in deliberative democracy depends less on simple presence than on the safeguards that make participation meaningful. In line with the literature, we note that young people are often underrepresented in formal politics yet comparatively receptive to issue-based and participatory forms of engagement. Deliberative spaces can therefore help build civic skills, confidence, and political efficacy, but they also risk reproducing inequalities by attracting those already predisposed to participate (Sloam, 2016; Checkoway, 2011; Bessant, 2020). For this reason, the field of applied deliberative democracy often fails to create "Viral Deliberation Chains", understood as interconnected deliberative processes that overlap and inform one another at different levels of governance, mobilising variable geometries of stakeholders that aggregate their views in a complementary, central process.

The comparative analysis shows several traditional responses to this dilemma, within the space of institutionalisation. Ireland and Scotland used creative and youth-centred methods to make deliberation safe and engaging. Brussels offered participants aged over 16 an unusual opportunity to deliberate on equal footing with elected representatives. France's Convention on the Time of the Child pushed inclusion further by designing age-differentiated formats for children and adolescents. Democratic Odyssey showed that younger participants can reshape deliberation when the deliberative space reaches refugee and asylum-seeker participants, as well as activist networks. A broader consideration that emerges is that deliberative democracy can deepen youth engagement, but only when recruitment, facilitation, and follow-up mechanisms are designed to prevent tokenism and convert voice into influence. Additionally, building on the materialist critiques raised in the first part of the paper, we also point to additional research avenues focusing on the role that youth may play in reimagining the management of capital accumulation and more sustainable global supply chains. Not from a regulatory side, i.e. deliberating exclusively with policymakers, but within processes of production (e.g. workers' co-operative models).

Overall, deliberative processes have often been deployed at various level of governance due to their ability to connect people in hybrid spaces (online, offline or both) and allow participants to empathise reciprocally. "Empathy" Muradova argues, "requires an *activation of people's affective empathic reactions*, not only their active

willingness to take a perspective. Empathy as a multidimensional emotion incorporates both cognitive (actively putting oneself into someone else's shoes) and affective (the feelings of warmth and concern felt toward the other) dimensions and the two are intertwined and work in tandem" (2025, pp. 9). Due to their ability to tap into the political experience and attitudes of lay citizens in a way that deepens agonistic thinking towards acknowledging grievances and hopes, deliberative democracy has established itself as one of the most prominent, adaptable and widespread DIs.

iii. Digital democracy

Digital democracy is a cross-cutting field that does not compete with other democratic innovations but enables, scales and hybridises them. The discussion is built around four cases: (i) HowTheyVote.eu, a small Berlin-based civic tech initiative that structures and publishes European Parliament roll-call votes in accessible formats; (ii) Make.org, a civic tech company specialised in large-scale online consultations; (iii) Open Source Politics, which deploys the open-source participatory infrastructure of Decidim for consultations, petitions, and participatory budgeting; and (iv) Treecompany, a Belgian organisation combining voting advice applications, AI-moderated comment spaces, and digital-physical hybrid installations in public settings. Taken together, these cases capture different democratic functions, ranging from accountability and facilitation to the translation of citizen input into institutionally usable outputs.

A central contribution of this analysis lies in its reflections on youth engagement. We underlined that reaching young people online is not simply a matter of providing digital access. Rather, participation depends on whether platforms are designed around the actual digital habits of younger cohorts, whether interaction is low-threshold and attractive from the first click, and whether online participation is reinforced through offline outreach in schools, youth councils, festivals, or local media. In this respect, Treecompany's digital installations and voting advice applications, Make.org's emphasis on user-centred design, and Open Source Politics' scalable and diffusible infrastructures, all suggest that digital democracy works best when it connects usability, facilitation, and political relevance. At the same time, we stressed that "digital native" does not automatically mean digitally literate: digital democracy may broaden access while reproducing inequalities linked to literacy, attention, and outreach capacity (Sgueo, 2023).

The broader lessons from the case studies are twofold. Digital tools can help young citizens understand politics more concretely, for instance by tracing how MEPs vote, or by translating public input into actionable formats. Nevertheless, their democratic value depends on institutional uptake, civic literacy, and hybrid links between online and offline participation. Additionally, as the field of civic tech expands rapidly and raises emerging ethical dilemmas regarding the pervasiveness of generative AI in the field, digital democracy is increasingly offered potential solutions to managing large-scale deliberations, simulate them altogether, or indeed conduct capacity-building activities through AI-powered facilitator training (Rountree and Gastil, 2026). As generative AI can also be an accelerator of structural inequality driven through lack of algorithmic fairness, its application across the four modes of public participation merits

constant reassessment. It is, in its essence, contingent upon human-centred design and should be designed as a corrective to consensus-making logics, i.e. a fairer and scalable way of including the underrepresented or indeed, those who do not have a voice (e.g. non-humans in climate change deliberations).

iv. Direct democracy

The field of direct democracy walks between two realms, one that belongs to the historical complementarity with electoral democracy and a second that adheres more canonically to imagining how direct democracy can be interfaced with other DIs. Some of the case studies we looked at point to direct democracy as being reconfigured and expanded upon, from referenda and citizens' initiatives to digitally enabled participation at national and transnational scale.

The analysis moves across four core cases. Brexit is treated as a cautionary example of the pathologies of consultative plebiscites, showing how direct voting on highly complex and polarised questions can compress competing preferences into a binary choice and expose the worst side of misinformation, disinformation, and intergenerational conflict. Switzerland, by contrast, represents the most institutionalised and routinised form of direct democracy in Europe, where repeated use of initiatives and referendums has embedded a stronger culture of participation and narrowed the distance between citizens and public officials. The chapter then turns to the innovative Chilean and Icelandic constitutional processes, both of which combined assembly-based drafting with a final popular vote but ultimately struggled to translate ambitious participatory design into durable constitutional change. Finally, the European Citizens' Initiative (ECI) is presented as the clearest experiment in scaling direct democracy to the transnational level, including through the voluntary follow-up to "Ending the Aviation Fuel Tax Exemption in Europe" initiative.

We underline that young people do not necessarily reject democracy as such, but often seek forms of participation that go beyond routinised electoral citizenship and connect more directly to high-stakes issues such as climate, education, research, and technological change. In that respect, direct democracy can provide a powerful mobilisation mechanism, as illustrated by the higher youth participation for the 2016 Brexit referendum, when compared with the 2015 UK general election. High-stakes collective decisions render the trade-offs more visible and the Brexit case displays how it contributed to set a positive trend of youth participation, leading to the so-called 'youthquake' during the 2017 General Elections (Curtice and Simpson, 2018). Yet we also stressed that mobilisation alone is not enough: without adequate design, deliberative safeguards, and credible political follow-through, direct voting can intensify frustration rather than deepen democratic inclusion.

We also looked at the Liquid Feedback case study as a practical entry point into the conceptual frameworks promoting liquid democracy. We underlined that its main innovation is voluntary delegation on a case by case basis: citizens can vote directly on issues they care about, while delegating other decisions to trusted actors. This model seeks to move beyond the blunt binary of conventional direct democracy, where citizens are often limited to a simple yes/no choice, by creating a more flexible relationship between direct and representative participation. In that sense, Liquid

Feedback retains the representative insight that not everyone will engage equally on every issue, while also opening space for the more selective, issue-based participation that characterizes political engagement of youth.

At the same time, we noted that the model is not without risks. In particular, long or opaque delegation chains may weaken democratic accountability and create a gap between participants' original preferences and final outcomes. For this reason, the chapter does not present liquid democracy as a ready-made institutional solution, but rather as a promising direction for thinking about more hybrid and adaptive systems of participation, especially in digital settings. It may hold relevance for youth engagement, since it aligns with more flexible and issue-driven forms of political action, while also requiring strong attention to digital literacy, inclusive design, and democratic safeguards.

v. Social movements and informal activism

In the report, we develop a specific analytical cluster on social movements and informal activism. This is an area where unconventional democratic innovations emerge quite strongly as the synthesis of grounded reflections on what works, engagement-wise. They epitomise how renewal can emerge from below, especially where formal institutions are weakened by democratic backsliding and shrinking civic spaces. The analysis focuses on three cases in Central and Eastern Europe: Amnesty International Hungary (AI Hungary), a more embedded NGO actor combining activist training, campaigns, and civic community-building; Tanítanék Mozgalom (the "I Would Teach Movement"), a Hungarian grassroots response to repression in education, mobilising teachers, parents, and students through civil disobedience and alliances; and Młodzieżowy Strajk Klimatyczny (MSK), the Polish branch of Fridays for Future, a decentralised youth climate movement linking school strikes and awareness-raising to broader questions of inequality and democratic vulnerability. Together, these cases illustrate different organisational forms (more formalised, grassroots, or youth-led) through which activism can sustain democratic innovation under hostile political conditions.

Drawing from the observations in Part I that young people are often not apathetic but selective, we note they are more likely to engage in issue-based, flexible, and non-committal forms of action than in routinised institutional participation. In this respect, social movements and informal activism can function as democratic laboratories, offering horizontal practices, civic learning, and new political languages that respond to low trust in institutions (Sloam, 2016). At the same time, we stressed the risks: tokenism, intimidation, burnout, and the tendency to recruit already-engaged youth rather than those most distant from politics (Bessant, 2004).

The comparison shows a productive tension between fluidity and embeddedness. IWTM and MSK are strongest in mobilising communities, generating intergenerational solidarity, and renewing democratic imaginaries around education and climate justice, but they remain vulnerable to discontinuity and weak political follow-up. Amnesty International Hungary, by contrast, offers continuity, training, and more stable organisational infrastructure, though at the cost of operating under intimidation and constrained policy leverage. We underlined that the transformative contribution of these movements lies less in immediate institutional reform than in prefiguring democracy: empowering youth, modelling horizontal cooperation,

and sustaining inclusive civic cultures even when formal responsiveness is low. The broader lesson is that democratic resilience may depend on hybridisation between informal activism and more embedded civic organisations.

Towards a taxonomy of democratic innovations

We are now in a position to ask how the examples of democratic innovations sketched above fit in a bigger picture before repositioning them within participatory chains. The sequencing of multiple DIs, we have argued, will also become more than the sum of its parts.

In order to systematically ask the question of how DIs can be part of broader democratic assemblages, we need to distinguish two key dimensions.

The first is formality, which we understand as a range between pure informality and highly formalised participation.

The second is temporal durability, which differentiates participatory designs targeting ad-hoc activities from more permanent variations. commonalities in (non-)permanence and (non-)formality.

This typology is useful in particular for highlighting similarities between our five main families of DIs (electoral, deliberative, digital, direct, social movements and informal activism). This ultimately opens to a deeper level of comparative analysis regarding power asymmetries, ranges of participation and DI sequencing. The case studies qualified in the matrix (Fig. 1) are available in Annex I, along with the corresponding acronyms as these are displayed in the matrix itself.

Fig. 1 The DI grid

Source: Authors' elaboration

Crossing these two dimensions we obtain four relevant categories which themselves may sometimes form a relevant sequence as part of one of our archetypal participatory chains.

i. Informal Ad-hoc (e.g. grassroots spontaneous mobilisation)

The informal-ad hoc quadrant represents forms of democratic innovation that are neither institutionalised, nor designed for long-term continuity. These practices typically emerge in response to immediate demands and concrete grievances, political crises, or perceived failures of representation. Their temporal presence is confined to specific moments and their legitimacy derives from mobilised publics rather than formalised mandates. Yet despite their short term nature and often symbolic subsidiarity, such initiatives often play a decisive role in shaping the participatory chain through agenda-setting, catalysation of formal initiatives, amplifying citizens' voice and reframing the public discourse. Their democratic value lies in mobilisation, experimentation, and norm creation, rather than formal, institutional durability. On the other hand, when repeated over time they can create commitment from those mobilised impressions in the broader public, raising the question of what “permanence” or “durability” actually means.

Generalising from our empirical cases, examples would include spontaneous demonstrations, digital campaigns, or grassroots assemblies often reacting to specific crises. This is the typical space of activism and social movements, often reinforced by digital democracy tools for coordination, mobilisation and strengthened visibility.

The “I Would Teach” movement in Hungary (IWTM) mobilised teachers and supporters around working conditions and education reform. Although not institutionalised, it catalysed nationwide debate and temporarily reconfigured alliances between unions, youth activists, and civil society actors. According to the co-founder of the movement, Katalin Törley (2025), the movement’s objectives evolved over time. “The overarching goal was to unite teachers, parents, and students into a civic front, recognising that change in education is inseparable from broader societal transformation, strengthened democratic norms and intersectoral solidarity within different interest and age groups.” While policy concessions are minimal, it renews civic language and prefigures democratic participation. Its organisational fragility did not exclude normative impact as it reframed public narratives around generational justice, and the value of public education. This underscores a key feature of the informal ad-hoc quadrant: durability may not reside in organisational continuity but in discursive continuity.

Similarly, the Polish Młodzieżowy Strajk Klimatyczny (Youth Climate Strike, MSK) provides strong empirical evidence exemplifying this quadrant. Emerging as part of the transnational Fridays for Future wave, it mobilised young people through school strikes, demonstrations, and digitally coordinated campaigns in Poland. Its structure was deliberately decentralised and fluid, relying on rapid digital communication and symbolic disruption rather than formal organisational hierarchy. While MSK is introducing climate justice to youth discourse, intersecting with struggles of various marginalized groups, it has a very limited policy uptake with minimal left-leaning support. According to an interviewee from the movement, “MSK serves the role of a “trampoline” for civic engagement; it is fostering public speaking and networking skills in the third sector from where youth activists can triangulate to other organizations” (Youth activist, 2025).

In matrix terms, there are other cases demonstrating how informal–ad-hoc mobilisation can exert vertical pressure on formal–permanent institutions. The European Citizens’ Initiative in Europe occupies an interesting borderline position. While the ECI instrument is formally institutionalised at EU level, mobilisation around specific initiatives often unfolds in an informal–ad-hoc manner through activist networks and temporary coalitions. The campaign phase thus resembles grassroots mobilisation even if the procedural endpoint is formal.

One notorious example is the Right2Water initiative that illustrates how informal-ad hoc grassroots mobilisation can trigger movement along the participatory chain toward institutionalised deliberation. Originating as a transnational citizen-led campaign, Right2Water mobilised over 1,8 million signatures without being embedded in formal decision-making structures. It eventually compelled the EU Commission to respond through hearings, formal policy deliberation, and subsequent revision of the EU Drinking Water Directive. In this sense, this initially informal mobilisation generated an institutionalised response that expanded formal participatory and deliberative engagement on water governance. This hybrid positioning illustrates how innovations can traverse quadrants within the participatory chain: informal mobilisation activates a formal mechanism, which may generate institutional follow-up.

Across these examples, digital infrastructures function as accelerators. Social media platforms, online petitions, and encrypted messaging groups lower coordination costs and enable rapid scaling across borders. However, the same fluidity that enables mobilisation also contributes to volatility. Informal–ad-hoc initiatives often dissolve once immediate

demand subsidy, and their translation into institutional reform is contingent on receptive political opportunity structures.

Analytically, the informal ad-hoc quadrant performs three systemic functions within democratic ecosystems:

1. **Agenda setting**, surfacing neglected issues and redefining political priorities.
2. **Norm prefiguration**, articulating new democratic expectations (e.g., intergenerational justice).
3. **Transmissive pressure**, compelling formal actors to adopt, adapt, or respond to social demands/crises, fostered through grassroots initiatives.

IWTM and MSK embody experimental, fluid, and prefigurative qualities of informal civic activism. Their strength lies in mobilising communities through horizontal practices, discursive agenda-setting, and the cultivation of new civic languages around education and climate justice. Despite limited policy impact, IWTM and MSK transform civic culture by renewing democratic imaginaries and fostering intergenerational solidarity (IWTM) or youth-led global-local linkages (MSK). Yet their highly operational, normative underlying assumptions make them highly vulnerable to governmental repression, activist burnout, and discontinuity.

Youth participation is particularly evident in this quadrant. Although young people are often seen as apathetic and disengaged, increased empirical evidence shows that young people are rather selective about how they engage and consider more carefully what specific actions they take. They prefer to 1) engage in action that does not require long-term commitment and 2) make sense in terms of cost-benefit calculation (Phelps, 2004). Therefore, non-institutional forms of democratic engagement (such as online engagement, protests, volunteering) are more popular among youth than institutional participation (e.g. party involvement). Youth are twice as likely to protest or engage online compared to older citizens, which indicates a shift from the ballot box to the digital square and the street (Markowski and Zagórski, 2025). Youth engagement in social movements also addresses low levels of trust in democratic institutions while fostering issue-based participation (Sloam, 2016). However, there is a significant risk of tokenism and attracting only already-engaged youth throughout these processes (Bessant, 2004).

Based both on our cases and the literature, we can safely state that informal ad-hoc mobilisation occupies a structurally liminal position in the participatory chain: they initiate claims in informal arenas that may later be absorbed into deliberative assemblies, party programs, or legislative reforms. Informal-ad-hoc mobilisation thus constitutes the entry point of many participatory trajectories. Rather than dismissing these practices as ephemeral, our matrix dimension encourages us to reinterpret them as catalytic instrumental platforms within a broader participatory chain. Their transformative potential depends less on permanence than on their capacity to trigger movement across all quadrants.

ii. Formal Ad-hoc (e.g. institutionalized but temporary)

The 'Formal Ad-hoc' quadrant includes a range of DIs that focus on temporary and yet formal pathways to participating in political life. On the one hand, it includes highly formal and ad hoc solutions, like a broad majority of the direct democracy formats (e.g. referenda) and the

rest of the legal frameworks enabling them. On the other it also embraces institutional attempts such as experimental assemblies mandated top-down, understood as experiments breaking with traditional infrastructures of electoral democracy. These DIs have two key characteristics that are of significant impact when assessing the design of participatory chains. Many, such as the direct democracy case study of the Irish Constitutional Convention (Gaiba, Hoppe, Moskovic, Nicolaidis, Pellegrini and Zgut-Przybylska, 2025), serve as culmination of a long and well-developed deliberative process. These cases pertain to a level of hybridity in design that already breaks away from a single DI and serve as counter-factual to essentialist formal-ad hoc cases. This already suggests interesting lessons for participatory chains.

Conversely, an exemplary case of a pure formal-ad hoc scenario would be the Brexit referendum, where the discursive shifts that occurred within a relatively brief period of time proved the high democratic volatility of the process. More importantly, this case study represents a form of DI that was considered highly innovative in past decades but can be argued to have been surpassed by more integrated infrastructures. In particular, the lack of a prolonged temporality becomes a core design issue in formal ad hoc mechanisms, as opposed to a strength. Additionally, cases of ad-hoc voting like the Brexit referendum demonstrated that episodic voting can be highly polarised and also have high impact on political imaginaries, identities and tensions.

As counters to the volatility risks, the other case studies explored within the 'formal ad-hoc' quadrant are less institutional, similarly intertwined with electoral democracy and yet more medium-to-long-term and stable. This is the case of the Belgian Socialist Party refoundation process, which epitomises the emergence of intra-party democratic innovations that are ad-hoc due to their experimental nature, while containing seeds of institutionalisation and formalisation. The latter seeds originate as a consequence of competition logics (i.e. if one party does it, others might) and as follow-up to a successful process. The Belgian Socialist Party's approach to harnessing the collective intelligence of its constituents to discuss core values and principles, is nested in an emerging tradition of parties (e.g. Podemos or 5 Star Movement) that bring forward a more formalised vision of deliberative integration.

Analytically, the formal-ad hoc quadrant encompasses three key functions:

1. **Decision-taking**, through tools and processes such as referenda
2. **Renewal of traditional structures of participation**, such as the deliberative turn within political parties or the digitalisation of e-voting within broader deliberative ecosystems
3. **Piloting normative proposals**, through experimentation without bindingness

In the case of the city of Barcelona, Bua and Bussu (2021) illustrate how a long-standing tradition of governance-driven democratisation (GDD) has led the city to develop a wide array of democratic innovation instruments (such as mini-publics) that served a very specific purpose. They qualify this as follows (Bua and Bussu, 2021, pp. 718): "The democratic potential of GDD therefore resides in its pragmatic, problem-solving orientation as well as its proximity to the 'nuts-and-bolts' of public administration." What is referenced in their analysis is a general tendency in scholarship and practice to focus to great extents on the consultative, formal and ad-hoc nature of some democratic innovations. This quadrant of our matrix is therefore filled with exemplary cases at multiple levels of governance, from the transnational (e.g. Conference on the Future of Europe) to the local. The analytical case

Bua and Bussu bring to the fore is particularly interesting because it emerges as a critique of this diffusion of short-lived and rather technocratic experiments, which tend to have a reductionist vision of political agonism and grassroots participation.

Nevertheless, the silver lining in the Barcelona case stands in the quality of the participation that was mobilised in a first phase by governance-driven democratisation (GGD), coupled with exogenous shocks coming from the 2008 financial crisis. In this context, the need for post-2008 interpretive frameworks, along with a crisis in the perceived legitimacy of institutions, led to what we consider a highly significant shift towards democracy-driven governance (DDG). Democracy-driven governance emerges in bottom-up spaces, where the sense of democratic ownership is more diffused. The particular case of Barcelona marks a shift from GGD to DDG at a specific time in the history of the city. This is when low trust in institutional attempts at participation (our formal ad-hoc category) impacted by their own inability to deliver demonstrable follow-up to participatory processes. As Bua and Bussu (2021) point out, the materialist critique introduced in Part I remains central to the analysis of these transitions, particularly at the local level and for technologically advanced cities. The experience of Barcelona prefigures a constant interaction and sometimes competition, between the 'formal ad-hoc' (GGD) and the 'informal permanent' (DDG).

iii. Informal-Permanent (e.g. established civil society and movements)

The informal-permanent quadrant contains non-institutionalized practices that persist outside formal political structures. Examples from our cases include Amnesty International as an embedded civil society case. More broadly, this paper considers long-standing NGOs, advocacy networks, or grassroots organizations that sustain engagement over time. Activism here consolidates into more permanent forms, sometimes overlapping with deliberative and/or digital innovations when movements institutionalize online platforms or deliberative practices internally. These actors are often more legitimate in the eyes of the broader public and likely to be supported over time. They provide stability, continuity, and normative depth, acting as watchdogs and reservoirs of democratic innovation beyond state structures.

If the informal-ad hoc quadrant captures the moment of ignition (when grassroots mobilisation, protest, or issue-based activism first generates visibility and political pressure) then the informal-permanent quadrant captures consolidation. It means the stabilisation of mobilisation into sustained networks, organised actors, and durable collective capacities that persist over time. Here we find actors and practices that are building organisational continuity, expertise, and normative authority. These include advocacy NGOs, long-standing activist networks, watchdog organisations, and digitally mediated civic platforms.

A paradigmatic example is Amnesty International that operates with enduring organisational structures, more stable fundings, and transnational coordination. Amnesty's legitimacy stems from sustained advocacy, research capacity, and moral authority rather than electoral mandate. In our matrix, Amnesty illustrates how activism can stabilise into durable civil infrastructure without crossing into "peek institutionalisation". Specific chapters like Amnesty International Hungary are also bridging global Amnesty frameworks with local action and projecting national advocacy back into European and transnational debates. Its transcalar

reach is therefore institutionalised but often limited by Hungary's restrictive civic space, where the government undercuts direct policy impact in a top-down authoritarian way.

AI Hungary's campaigns like "One Voice Is Not Enough" introduced new formats of civic dialogue, a street forum with direct citizen–lawyer interactions to challenge the dominance of authoritarian state-controlled narratives. In the words of its head of activism coordination: "In response to the Orbán- government's attempts to restrict freedom of assembly, AI Hungary (AI in Fig. 1) also organized training sessions in cities like Pécs and Debrecen, with participation exceeding usual levels" (Horváth, 2025). Additionally, local thematic groups (LGBTIQA+ rights, wage transparency, etc.) create "communities of action" that continue beyond single campaigns, providing continuity for activist engagement and community-building.

The global Amnesty movement's role in the Control Arms Campaign showcases how civil society can feed into formal multilateral decision-making processes by expanding deliberative participation on issues that were previously marginal in international law. Together with partners such as IANSA and Oxfam, Amnesty helped coordinate a global campaign with petitions, public actions, and public consultations to advocate for a legally binding Arms Trade Treaty (ATT). The overarching goal was to regulate the international trade in conventional weapons. After more than a decade of advocacy, this collective action shaped UN deliberations and ultimately resulted in the UN General Assembly's adoption of the ATT in 2013, a major normative and institutional response to demands for arms control. From the participatory chain aspect, this quadrant works primarily as a stabilising layer. While informal–ad-hoc initiatives may spark a momentum, informal–permanent actors provide organisational tools capable of sustaining claims over time and translating them into policy proposals. They often act as interlocutors between citizens, parliamentary processes and broader publics.

Informal–permanent actors therefore perform several distinct functions in democratic ecosystems:

1. **Normative continuity**, preserving issue salience when media attention fades away/does not even reach the threshold.
2. **Bridging functions**, connecting grassroots mobilisation with formal deliberative or legislative terrains
3. **Capacity building**, fostering training activists, producing expertise, and professionalising advocacy.

Youth participation remains central but takes a different form than in the informal-ad-hoc quadrant. Rather than episodic mobilisation, young activists may take up organisational roles, develop policy expertise, and engage in long-term advocacy. The generational dimension therefore shifts from ad-hoc protest to institutional memory within the civil sector. This way, informal–permanent structures become a springboard for democratic skills and leadership pipelines. Importantly, these actors keep autonomy from state organizations. Their independence can enhance legitimacy, particularly in contexts of democratic backsliding or declining trust in formal institutions. At the same time, their influence depends on access to funding, civic space protections, and political receptiveness which varies across space and time. Without mechanisms of uptake in formal–permanent arenas, even well-established civil society organisations risk marginalisation.

iv. Formal Permanent: (e.g. institutionalised and permanent)

The “Formal permanent” quadrant captures those democratic innovations that cease to operate as exceptional participatory correctives and instead become durable institutions of democratic life, with all the gains in continuity, visibility and learning this entails, but also with the incumbent risks of bureaucratisation, elite control and perfunctory inclusion.

An exemplary case of a highly formalised and permanent democratic innovation is the Ostbelgien Model (“OBM” in our matrix, Fig. 1). This process originated in the German-speaking region of Belgium and, like many successful case studies in each of our four quadrants, combined various DI stakeholders. First and foremost, this process did originate not by an institutional and perfunctory desire to pay lip service to citizen voices, or indeed by a consultative and top-down drive, but rather by a deeply substantiated need to renew democracy. The bottom-up role of the G1000 was significant, as its push for change in the aftermath of political stalemate at national level, along with a broader participatory impetus at multiple levels of governance (Nicolaidis, 2024), were crucial in the regional diffusion from Brussels to the Eastbelgien region (Niessen and Reuchamps, 2019).

In the Ostbelgien model, a Citizens’ Council is dedicated to the agenda-setting functions, and calls on a separate deliberative assembly to form and deliberate on the selected topic. The Council is also responsible for monitoring follow-up, once the assembly is completed and recommendations are formulated. This division of labour and responsibilities enables a clear mechanism where the citizens mutually acknowledge their different remits. The mechanism is particularly effective due to the embeddedness of public officials in the process. Despite initial concerns on bindingness of the output, the role of the ministers and of elected representatives is clearly laid out, as is the framework for their feedback on how they will follow up to recommendations (Niessen and Reuchamps, 2022).

The Ostbelgien model provides an exemplary case to demonstrate how the ‘formal permanent’ typology, like all other three, not only contains single DIs, but rather a weighted combination of them. The model converges towards a sequence of two-tiered deliberative democracy (through the Citizens’ Council and the deliberative assembly), along with a new way for electoral democracy to engage with decision-making processes. To proceed comparatively, and as discussed in the case of ‘permanent ad hoc’ example of Barcelona, the lack of stacked DIs with embedded and meaningful presence of policymakers led to struggles in institutionalisation. More generally, formal and permanent democratic innovations can emerge incrementally from the previous quadrant of ‘informal-permanent’ innovations.

On top of the three functions already enlisted as characteristic of ideal-type ‘informal-permanent’ participatory chains (normative continuity, bridging, capacity building), the formal–permanent ones also offers:

1. **Wide embeddedness opportunities**, fostering and a deeper pedagogy of citizen participation
2. **Boosted transparency and accountability**, as citizen-washing by institutions and formal bodies becomes less sustainable in permanent processes

3. **Lower material and immaterial costs** due to standardised opportunities for the wider public to engage, as well as reduction of costs emerging from non-impermanence and consolidated implementation workflows

A mixed approach is to embed youth-led civil society in a 'permanent-formal' process set up by institutions. This is the case of the EU Youth Dialogue, with mixed results. In this process, participation is channelled through youth organisations, which collect interests and select delegates to take part in the process. The EU Youth Dialogue process has major institutional engagement led by the European Steering Committee. The Committee is composed of representatives of the European Commission (EC), the European Youth Forum and the country holding the Presidency of the Council of the EU (Pušnik, 2023). The major shortfall of this type of DI is its struggle to genuinely empower grassroots participation and to generate an intergenerational and transformative vision for the future. Of course, the agenda-setting being directly in the hands of the organisers staggers the potential and is in direct contrast with the the Ostbelgien model just reviewed. This reflects a general top-down approach to youth participation, which crystallises and formalises it in rather static ways (Pušnik, 2023).

One of the disempowering mechanisms at play is constructed through the excessive placement of representative responsibility on the youth that takes part, as well as a discursive framework that alienates them from their non-participating peers. Pušnik (2023) identifies this as a systematic approach to engaging youth voices in a way that builds on constraining mechanisms, where the voice of youth needs to be adapted to the formal tone institutions expect to receive. In top-down consultations, the translation of preferences to policy-making jargon hinders the ability to be legitimately representative of their peers, as well as to disrupt inherent power hierarchies (Pušnik, 2023). Additionally, the visibility offered by such a process remains marginal, as the output stays consultative.

A final note on this typology of DIs traces back to some of the materialist critiques anticipated in Part I. The philanthropic sector has an emerging role supporting the experimental DIs but is also reorganising at a meta-level to operate through DIs. For instance, 'participatory grantmaking' (PGM) opens to new spaces and timelines for engagement of vulnerable communities, in ways that include the meta-design of the agenda-setting process itself (Hauger, 2023). In this sense, we observe a potential cleavage between DIs promoted by the public sector versus the philanthropic one. This materialises both in the different range of research on the topic, but also in terms of the differentiation in formalisation discourses. Against this backdrop, the distinction between 'formal' and 'institutional' becomes critically important. In our matrix, we track for formalisation as a broader category that also encompasses institutionalisation, albeit not limited to it.

Current research on the broader theory and practice of embeddedness indicates precisely this trend. Institutionalisation (e.g. through legal frameworks) can be one way of imagining formalisation (e.g. broader set of rules and standards), which in turn can lead to even wider embeddedness if multiple contextual factors are met. The factors that ensure embeddedness are spatial ('where'), temporal ('when'), and related to practices ('how'), as conceptualised by Bussu et al (2022).

Cross-quadrant DIs

The intuition behind our three archetypal participatory chains is reflected in this section which offers many more such (at least partial) chains. We find that the five families of democratic innovations do not fit neatly into single quadrants but instead move across the matrix depending on their degree of formalisation and permanence. The matrix is therefore useful not as a rigid classification tool, but as a way of showing how democratic innovations interact, evolve, and overlap within a broader participatory ecosystem.

Electoral democracy innovations are generally expected to cluster in the **formal** quadrants because they affect the institutional core of democratic systems, such as parliaments, electoral rules, and party structures. Reforms like lowering the voting age or changing electoral systems are usually highly visible and difficult to reverse. However, some electoral innovations also emerge in more temporary, ad-hoc contexts, often under pressure from activism, and their long-term institutionalisation may remain uncertain.

Deliberative democracy is presented as especially spread across the matrix. When citizens' assemblies or councils become linked to parliaments or other institutions, they tend to belong to the **formal-permanent** quadrant. Yet many deliberative practices remain one-off or experimental, occupying the **formal-ad hoc** space. This reflects the dual role of deliberation as both a temporary corrective and a possible long-term complement to representative democracy. When deliberative democracy serves as an accelerator of methodological and substantive change, it can take more experimental forms in the **informal-ad hoc** space.

Digital democracy is more dispersed as it is understood as a more horizontal process facilitation layer. Informal digital platforms for crowdsourcing, online campaigning, and mobilization often fall into the **informal-ad hoc** quadrant, while more institutionalised e-consultation systems and EU-level participatory portals may shift toward the **formal-permanent** side. This confirms the cross-cutting, enabling role of digital tools.

Direct democracy can also move between quadrants. Referenda and citizens' initiatives are often formalised and embedded in institutions, but they can also be activated only temporarily through single-issue campaigns.

Finally, activism and social movements are mainly located in the **informal** quadrants, beginning as reactive and often short-lived forms of mobilisation, though some become more enduring. Overall, the matrix highlights that democratic innovations overlap and feed into one another rather than exist as isolated types. It also tells us that to start addressing the question of participatory chains, we ought to look through the lenses of the quadrants as the most effective way of identifying combinations of formality and permanence.

Part III: Pathways to transformative participatory chains

As we have largely explored in a more detailed landscaping of DIs carried out in 2025 (Gaiba, Hoppe, Moskovic, Nicolaidis, Pellegrini and Zgut-Przybylska), democratic innovations are often developed and applied in pro-cyclical design formats. This approach to sandboxing marginal innovation arguably aggravates the risks of democratic stagflation presented in the first part of this paper. We argue it prevents from engaging with bold, transcalar innovations in governance, which requires rethinking the structural way in which we deploy and experience democratic participation through archetypal participatory chains. This can be done by dovetailing democratic innovations, but with an eye to how this empowers youth to reclaim the richness of democratic assemblage.

For one, we argue that social movements and activist networks play an important integrative role within democratic innovation ecosystems, while youth participation operates as a transversal force that cuts across these spaces. Movements are dynamic arenas in which new claims, repertoires of participation, and normative expectations are articulated and tested, some of which later enter institutional channels. Young people are particularly prominent within these processes: they often engage first through issue-based mobilisation, digital activism, and informal collective action, before - or instead of - participating in formal institutional design. Therefore, youth engagement frequently travels across sites of participation, linking activism and institutional innovations, and thereby shaping how democratic practices diffuse and transform. At a more general level, we argue that the space of informal participation, if ignored, will fail to generate wide interest for youth.

Building on this argument, we conceptualise structural innovations in democracy as a participatory chain of multiple, interdependent layers of engagement. Activist arenas contribute especially to agenda formation and claim articulation, while institutional mechanisms provide structured settings for deliberation, decision-making, and formalisation. Youth participation traverses this chain, often acting as a bridge between informal and formal modes of engagement as well as between digital, street-level, and institutionalised practices. The relationship among these spheres is neither hierarchical nor linear, and it involves selective uptake and friction. Our goal is to analyse how democratic innovation emerges from the interaction of institutional and informal forms of participation, making hybridity and generational dynamics structural features of democratic renewal.

Activism at the core

Activism is the most transformative category of all, although its staying power is often wanting. This is why we have found it at the core of all of our three archetypal participatory chains, most durable when no longer unfolding alone. Movements for social or climate justice, racial or gender equality, anti-corruption or anti-nepotism all generate new kinds of demands not easily accommodated by traditional electoral democracy. Activists are the most prone to experimenting with democratic practices (Dahl, 1989). They can hold grassroots assemblies, use digital coordination and affect electoral agendas (Della Porta, 2020). Activism overlaps with electoral democracy when movements evolve into increasingly intersectional organisations or new kinds of parties.

At a minimum activists can reshape the agendas of political parties, as the case of the Belgian Socialist Party discussed above has shown, as well as pressure governments to

establish citizens' assemblies, which admittedly opens up logics in competition with traditional electoral politics. Social and activist movements tend to use direct-democratic instruments more than traditional politics. In Europe they are much more prone to support citizens' initiatives than the actors connected to electoral democracy (Right2Water campaign). In general, they seek to institutionalize claims that might otherwise remain oppositional – but such institutionalisation does not necessarily need to happen within structure. In this sense, activism functions as both a transformative engine of innovation across the board and as a corrective, ensuring that institutional reforms remain anchored in citizen lived experience and social mobilisation.

The above examples are but one set of participatory chains that we have observed structured together. There are, however and perhaps obviously, many chains combining permanent and temporary, formal and informal innovations to establish structural chains. There are also numerous ways in which external circumstances as well as the local / national contexts structure the possibility space in which chains play out. Our intent with this theoretical contribution is to offer analytical clarity as well as creative ways to support innovation for thriving democracies.

Normative correctives

We have argued that traditional responses to our democratic crisis whether centred on electoral reform, deliberative mini-publics or digital engagement have tended to operate within relatively discrete paradigms of democratic innovation. Yet, taken in isolation, each of these approaches appears insufficient to address the systemic and multi-layered nature of current legitimacy failures (Smith, 2009). The hybridisation of democratic practices articulating electoral, deliberative, participatory, digital, and activist forms might offer a systemic response to contemporary legitimacy failures.

Rather than privileging a single democratic mode, the hybridisation of DIs recognises that legitimacy emerges from the interaction of multiple, mutually reinforcing mechanisms. Electoral reforms can open institutional space for deliberation; deliberative processes can, in turn, legitimise informed referenda; digital platforms can connect informal participation to formal decision-making; and activism operates as a “connective tissue” sustaining democratic engagement across contexts, particularly when institutional channels are weakened. In this sense, democratic innovation should be seen as an adaptive ecosystem. However, this ecosystem currently suffers from weak institutional linkages. Democratic processes are too often confined to isolated governance levels or remain disconnected from formal decision-making. Reasserting the need for stronger institutional articulation across local, national, and European levels is therefore a central normative imperative. Without such linkages, democratic innovations risk becoming symbolic, failing to address the deeper legitimacy crisis they are meant to resolve.

Within this broader framework, the intergenerational lens constitutes a critical normative corrective. Contemporary democracies remain structurally biased toward present constituencies, systematically underrepresenting younger generations and future interests. Embedding youth participation within hybrid democratic ecosystems through youth assemblies, intergenerational fora, and flexible forms of activism introduces a principle of intergenerational fairness that rebalances democratic voice over time. This implies

recognising participation not merely as an opportunity but as a civic right, supported by enabling measures such as “citizenship leave,” resources for youth engagement, and safeguards against intimidation.

Hybrid democratic ecosystems also hold significant potential to mitigate democratic backsliding. By diversifying sites of participation and embedding deliberative norms across institutional and informal arenas, they reduce reliance on electoral majorities or executive dominance. At the same time, they can counter polarisation and disinformation by fostering reasoned, inclusive, and transparent forms of collective decision-making. Yet this potential remains contingent: without sustained political will, adequate funding, and robust follow-up mechanisms, democratic innovations risk being depoliticised or instrumentalised, ultimately undermining their transformative capacity.

Added Value of Archetypal Participatory Chains

As outlined in Part II democratic innovations can be usefully analysed along two dimensions: their degree of institutionalisation (formal vs. informal) and their temporality (ad hoc vs. permanent). This distinction helps clarify the specific roles they play within our archetypal participatory chains.

Informal ad hoc DIs correspond to a fluid space of counter-hegemonic experimentation, where bottom-up participation can emerge rapidly, politicise new issues, and challenge dominant agendas, albeit often with limited durability and direct policy impact. They are of course key to our first archetypal chain, e.g. Insurgent-to-Institutional chains. But they can also feed Viral Deliberation Chains and Counter-Power Chains.

Informal and permanent constitute the social infrastructure of democratic life and we refer to these participatory chains as the stabilising layer. Civil society organisations and activist networks sustain engagement over time, ensuring continuity, capacity-building, and pressure on institutions thereby acting as a key driver of democratic renewal. These DIs constitute the intermediary building blocks of Insurgent-to-Institutional chains. They also feed Viral Deliberation Chains and Counter-Power Chains.

Formal and ad hoc such as referendums or one-off citizens’ assemblies, create punctual openings in the political system. They can generate important discursive shifts and broaden participation, but also contribute to the volatility of engagement when not embedded in longer-term processes. These DIs prefigure structural change and bode well with Viral Deliberation Chains, but often fail to scale to systematically activate Insurgent-to-Institutional chains. Most of these DIs originate from underlying counter-power narratives but open-up to the role of activism and social movements less prominently.

Formal and permanent institutions represent the most structurally embedded dimension of democratic innovation. While they offer stability and the potential for routinised participation, their effectiveness depends on their embeddedness and complementarity with more dynamic and informal forms. Without such articulation, they risk becoming hollowed out and disconnected from broader societal dynamics. They are key to Counter-Power Chains our second archetypal chain, and the destination of Insurgent-to-Institutional chains. And they are also key to the durability of what we have called Viral Deliberation Chains.

Taken together, these four configurations highlight the need to allow for, empower or design participatory chains that combine stability with openness, and institutionalisation with societal anchoring.

Building on this framework, our ideal-type participatory chain can also be understood as a sequenced process in which different democratic instruments are mobilised at distinct stages to maximise both inclusion and impact. The concept of a “participatory chain” provides an analytical and practical framework for structuring hybrid democracy into a coherent and scalable system. It responds directly to a key limitation identified in the literature on democratic innovations, namely their tendency to remain institutionally bounded and weakly interconnected (Smith, 2009; Warren, 2017). By contrast, the participatory chain emphasises the importance of linking participatory processes across governance levels and policy stages, ensuring that citizen input is not only generated but also transmitted, translated, and effectively acted upon. In doing so, it echoes broader calls for systemic coherence within deliberative systems (Mansbridge et al., 2012).

A well-designed participatory chain strengthens responsiveness and political uptake by embedding clear feedback loops and accountability mechanisms. This concern aligns with longstanding critiques of participatory governance, which warn against the risks of tokenistic or consultative exercises disconnected from actual decision-making power (Fung, 2006). Citizen contributions, whether emerging from deliberative mini-publics or digital platforms, must therefore be explicitly linked to formal decision-making procedures, with visible commitments from political actors to respond. Without such articulation, participatory processes risk losing credibility, reinforcing disillusionment, and ultimately undermining the broader wave of democratic innovation. Importantly, the participatory chain also highlights the role of activism as a resilience layer. Social movements sustain engagement, maintain pressure on institutions, and keep democratic innovations alive when formal mechanisms are curtailed or deprioritised. Supporting flexible forms of youth activism through funding, mentorship, and institutional recognition is therefore essential to ensuring the continuity and adaptability of the democratic ecosystem.

This systemic ambition, however, also brings into focus a set of structural constraints related to the interaction between participatory processes and institutional decision-making. As noted by Bua and Bussu (2021, pp.726), “collaboration with institutions might be a necessary condition for policy impact, but it is not a sufficient one, because the state imposes administrative dynamics that can halt change.” This insight highlights a core tension within participatory chains: while institutional anchoring is essential to ensure political uptake, it simultaneously exposes participatory processes to bureaucratic inertia, political filtering, and constraints that may dilute or block their transformative potential. In this sense, the very mechanisms designed to secure responsiveness and accountability can also generate new forms of friction, particularly when participatory outputs must circulate across different arenas, actors, and decision-making logics. These challenges become even more pronounced when participatory chains seek to articulate heterogeneous democratic instruments, raising questions about how different forms of legitimacy, knowledge, and authority can be effectively combined within a coherent system.

Yet, when implemented in practice, participatory chains reveal a set of structural tensions stemming from the articulation of heterogeneous democratic instruments particularly when

combining deliberative mini-publics with direct democratic tools such as referendums. A recurrent concern in the literature is the epistemic asymmetry between participants in deliberative processes who benefit from structured learning, expert input, and extended deliberation and the broader electorate, which may not have access to comparable conditions of informed judgement (Fishkin, 2009; Lafont, 2020). This asymmetry can generate reluctance among mini-public participants to submit complex or carefully balanced recommendations to a referendum, out of concern that they may be simplified, misunderstood, or rejected in a less deliberative public sphere. Empirical accounts of citizens' assemblies confirm this tension, showing that participants often develop a strong sense of ownership over their recommendations and question the capacity of mass voting processes to adequately reflect informed preferences (Courant, 2021).

This challenge is illustrated by the French Citizens' Convention for Climate, where some participants expressed opposition to submitting certain proposals to a referendum, arguing that the broader public had not benefited from the same deliberative conditions and might therefore not fully grasp the trade-offs involved. Such reactions highlight a broader "deliberative vs. aggregative" tension within democratic theory, where the legitimacy derived from inclusive participation may conflict with the legitimacy derived from mass electoral endorsement (Lafont, 2020). Rather than reinforcing each other automatically, different democratic tools may thus operate according to distinct logics that are not always easily reconciled within a single participatory chain.

A related limitation concerns the translation of deliberative assemblies outputs into referendum questions by political actors. The case of the 2024 Irish constitutional referendums on family and care, which followed earlier deliberative processes including a citizens' assembly, illustrates how deviations in wording and framing can significantly affect outcomes. When political authorities reformulate or selectively adapt recommendations, they may unintentionally weaken their coherence or legitimacy, contributing to public confusion or mistrust (Suiter et al., 2016; Farrell et al., 2019). The rejection of proposed constitutional changes in this case underscores how fragile the link can be between deliberative mini-publics and direct democracy mechanisms, particularly when the chain of transmission is not perceived as faithful or transparent.

Taken together, these examples suggest that participatory chains should not be understood solely as the stacking of multiple democratic instruments, but rather as the engineering of complex configurations requiring careful institutional design. This is only more challenging when connecting translocal participation across Europe, with EU-level governance. Ensuring alignment between deliberative processes and referendums may require additional intermediary steps such as broader public deliberation, enhanced information campaigns, or co-designed question framing to mitigate epistemic gaps and preserve the integrity of citizen input. Without such safeguards, the integration of different tools risks generating friction rather than coherence, ultimately weakening DI integration and democratic uptake.

A roadmap for future EU democratic innovation should build on the participatory chain approach while explicitly addressing the tensions identified between deliberative and aggregative mechanisms. At the European level, this implies moving beyond isolated pilot projects toward an integrated architecture that sequences citizen participation across agenda-setting, decision-making, and follow-up. Deliberative mini-publics such as those

convened under the Conference on the Future of Europe should be institutionally anchored with clear mandates, follow-up procedures, and formal links to legislative and executive processes. To mitigate epistemic asymmetries, their outputs should be complemented by broader public deliberation phases, including accessible information campaigns, digital deliberation platforms, and transnational debates, before any potential recourse to EU-wide or national referendums. Crucially, the integrity of the participatory chain must be preserved through transparent translation mechanisms, ensuring that recommendations are not substantially altered without justification, and that political actors remain accountable for their uptake or rejection. Embedding these processes within EU governance would also require dedicated funding streams, administrative capacity, and inter-institutional coordination, as well as stronger recognition of civil society and social movements as continuity actors within the system.

In this perspective, democratic innovation in the EU should be conceived not as a series of experiments, but as the gradual construction of a resilient, multi-level deliberative system capable of reconciling inclusiveness, epistemic quality, and political effectiveness. Additionally, the general and growing fluidity of democratic participation across borders, raises a broader question of transcalarity in governance. Particularly for youth engagement. Constructing archetypal participatory chains means enabling the convergence of translocal networks of 'informal-permanent' DIs with a EU-level trajectory towards 'formal-permanent' processes (Conference on the Future of Europe, European Citizen Panels). It also means empowering 'informal-permanent' and 'informal-ad hoc' DIs to promote incremental changes to the 'formal-permanent', as they have been observed to raise structural critiques of the DIs' status quo. In this context, the 'formal-ad hoc' DIs serve as the culmination of some of these 'participatory chains', with voting moments on direct issues the EU polities will have advocated for, or deliberated and negotiated on. Sustainable pathways to follow-up remain the most underexplored in research and practice, outside of consolidated and cross-quadrant case studies like the embeddedness of the deliberative Ostbelgien model, the legal-administrative bindingness of some direct democracy instruments (e.g. post-deliberation plebiscites or mandatory referenda), or the adaptive mechanisms of informal-permanent networks.

Ultimately, our research emerges from this vision of the different types of participation and seeks to take stock of individual DIs. These are placed conceptually on the conveyer belt of participatory sequencing, which we defined as 'participatory chains'. Further research could also focus more structurally on connecting participatory processes and participatory research, tapping into the epistemic wealth that emerges from a wide range experiments in DIs (Asenbaum et al, 2025). Inter alia, this paper is developed within a Horizon Europe-funded project and addresses the question of how to make sense of participatory proliferation, with an eye to identifying participatory value through optimal participatory chains. Yet it is important to note that our starting point is not to imagine a reduction in the participatory effervescence already present. There is intrinsic value in many case studies that pilot the objectives of scaling and draw both from successes and failures (Daminov, Liebert, Povse et al, 2025). These cases belong to the world of risk-taking experimentations in the ways Asenbaum et al (2025) argue. They often build on hybrid methodologies in which participatory research, also within a broad consortium of epistemic actors - belonging to the academic and practitioner world - design participatory processes on the ground. We recommend further connecting the worlds of research and practice through semi-formal

infrastructures (e.g. further consolidation of academic observation networks to participatory processes).

Conclusion

We have argued that contemporary democracies are increasingly characterised by a condition that can be described as democratic stagflation. Borrowing from macroeconomic terminology, this concept captures the confluence of stagnation in the quality and impact of participatory processes, alongside an inflation in the costs and barriers associated with democratic participation.

On the stagnation side, participatory quality remains limited. Many democratic innovations operate in isolation, often addressing single-issue policy questions without being embedded in broader policy cycles. Intersectional and structural issues continue to be primarily articulated through protest movements rather than through institutionalised participatory channels. Moreover, when democratic innovations are implemented by public authorities, they are frequently deployed within a consultative logic that does not structurally connect them to decision-making processes or require demonstrable political follow-up. As a result, the incentives for citizens to participate, remains weak. Much like stagnant wages in economic stagflation, the “returns” of participation whether in terms of influence, recognition, or policy impact are low, while citizens face increasing trade-offs in allocating their time and resources to political engagement.

At the same time, an inflationary dynamic affects access to democratic goods. Meaningful opportunities to shape collective decisions remain scarce relative to citizens’ democratic expectations. The direct and hidden costs of participation continue to increase, particularly in a context where emergency politics and crisis governance concentrate decision-making power and the growing number of DIs does not affect it.

For institutional actors, launching new democratic innovations can also entail political risks, including loss of agenda control or heightened public scrutiny. These pressures may produce undesirable side effects: innovators may reduce the quality and deliberative depth of participatory processes in order to make them easier to organise, while citizens may gravitate toward the most accessible and low-commitment forms of engagement rather than toward more demanding but potentially more impactful participatory formats.

This dual dynamic creates a structural trap: democratic participation becomes simultaneously less impactful and more costly, thereby undermining its capacity to renew democratic legitimacy. Overcoming democratic stagflation therefore requires moving beyond isolated participatory experiments toward the construction of coherent participatory ecosystems that reduce participation costs while increasing its political effectiveness. In this paper, we propose three archetypal participatory chains that may better connect governance levels, ensure continuity between local, national, and transnational processes, and embed clear mechanisms for political uptake and accountability. Such systems are built to increase effectiveness and therefore, incentives. Our further analysis on the formal-informal and

permanent-ad hoc nature of Dis, reveals how seeds of meaningful participatory chains are already present, but their mapping requires analytical rigour and a robust research agenda.

Looking forward, we argue that the consolidation of an evidence base for hybrid democratic ecosystems will also benefit from further widening the gaze to non-European case studies. This includes longitudinal studies exploring the long-term effects of archetypal participatory chains on trust, legitimacy, and policy outcomes; the exploration of AI-powered DIs and the implications for inclusiveness and quality of discourse; and the analysis of youth activism in contexts of democratic erosion.

Finally, these normative and analytical advances call for systematic empirical testing. The European Union is uniquely positioned to act as a laboratory for democratic innovation by piloting participatory chains and hybrid democratic models across its multi-level governance system. Embedding such pilots within a broader EU democratic innovation agenda would not only generate valuable evidence but also contribute to addressing legitimacy deficits and strengthening democratic resilience across the Union in ways that mainstream youth participation.

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Annex I

The list of exemplary DI case studies that feeds our DI matrix

Deliberative Committees in Brussels	DC
Democratic Odyssey	DO

French Convention (temps de l'enfant)	FC
Refondation du Parti Socialialiste	RPS
Children and Youth Assembly in Scotland and Ireland	CYA
Lowering the voting age	Vote16
EU Youth Dialogue	EUYD
EU Youth Test	EYT
Advisory Council on Youth	AC
Brexit referendum	Brexit
"Ending the Aviation Fuel Tax Exemption in Europe" ECI	EAFT-ECI
Amnesty International	AI
I would teach movement	IWTM
Młodzieżowy Strajk Klimatyczny	MSK
Assemblée libre des jeunes	AJL
Moldova Citizens Assembly	MCA
Agora Brussels	AGO
Burgerdialog Ostbelgien	OBM

DECIDIM	DCDM
Purpoz	Purpoz
Consul Democracy	CONSUL
Forum against Fakes	FAF
Fridays for Future	FFF
EurHope	EH
Democratic Commons	DC (yellow)
Europa, jetzt wird's konkret!	EJWSK
Youth Climate Assembly in Ida-Viru	YCAIIV
Declic	DEC
mZaednica	MZA
Moj Grad	MOJ
Howtheyvote.eu	HTV
Make.org	MAKE
Open Source Politics	OSP
Treecompany.be	TREE

Source: Authors' elaboration